

Synthesis and characterization of organotin(IV) complexes of 2-phenylphenol

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Abstract : The *n*-dibutyl and triphenyltin(IV) complexes of composition $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_{2-x}(\text{OAr})_x$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})$ (where $\text{OAr} = \text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{-Ph-2}$; $x = 1$ and 2) have been synthesized in quantitative yields by the reaction of their respective chlorides, $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and Ph_3SnCl with trimethylsilyl derivative of 2-phenylphenol in carbon tetrachloride. On the other hand, the good yields of the complexes of composition $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}_{2-x}(\text{OAr})_x$ and $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})$ have been obtained from the reaction of Me_2SnCl_2 and $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ with 2-phenylphenol in the presence of Et_2NH in tetrahydrofuran. The characterization of the complexes has been accomplished by elemental analyses, molar conductance measurements, molecular weight determinations and IR, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{119}Sn NMR and mass spectral methods. The thermal behaviour of the complexes has been studied by TG-DTA techniques. The reactions of parent complexes with nitrogenous bases viz. imidazole and benzimidazole have yielded 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molecular adducts authenticated by physicochemical and IR spectral data.

Keywords : Organotin(IV) complexes, 2-phenylphenol, nitrogenous bases, imidazole, benzimidazole.

Introduction

The organotin complexes possess unique and considerable potential owing to their vast industrial, agricultural and medicinal applications¹. On the other hand, of various ligands known for the synthesis of metal complexes, the use of substituted phenols has been of particular interest as the variations in the phenolic ligand periphery offer not only the dramatic changes in physical and chemical properties of their compounds but also provide rich structural chemistry and coordination geometries². Phenols also find extensive use as antioxidants, catalysts and exhibit biological activity. Literature survey reveals that compared to voluminous reports on transition metal phenoxides², only a few scattered reports describe the synthesis of organotin(IV) complexes of phenol³ despite the fact that organotin(IV) phenoxides are known to display antibacterial activity and form an important constituent of catalytic systems⁴. In continuation of our earlier work on the synthesis of organotin(IV) phenoxides⁵, the present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of organotin(IV) complexes of unexplored 2-phenylphenol which is known to possess antibacterial and antifungal properties and has been reported to control the post harvest diseases of several variety of fruits⁶. The reactivity of newly synthesized complexes with nitrogenous bases has also been studied.

Results and discussion

The synthetic routes which led to the isolation of di- and tri-organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides in quantitative yields can be represented as :

The analytical data for the complexes are listed in Table 1 and conform to the proposed molecular formulae. The dimethyl and triphenyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides are white to light yellow coloured solids while di- and tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) analogues are colourless liquids. The com-

Table 1. Analytical data of organotin(IV) complexes

Complex (Molecular formula)	Colour	Yield (%)	m.p./b.p.* (°C)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Molar cond. in PhNO ₂ (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
				Sn	Cl	C	H	N		
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(OAr) (C ₂₀ H ₂₇ ClOSn)	Colourless	89	145*	27.28 (27.20)	8.67 (8.11)	55.01 (54.86)	6.20 (6.17)	-	858 (437.5)	0.85
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ Sn(OAr) ₂ (C ₃₂ H ₃₆ O ₂ Sn)	Colourless	90	142*	21.08 (20.84)	-	67.44 (67.25)	6.34 (6.30)	-	580 (571)	0.80
Me ₂ SnCl(OAr) (C ₁₄ H ₁₅ ClOSn)	Yellow	71	210 (dec.)	34.17 (33.66)	10.3 (10.0)	47.91 (47.52)	4.1 (4.24)	-	712 (353.5)	1.15
Me ₂ Sn(OAr) ₂ (C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₂ Sn)	Creamish white	77	178 (dec.)	25.01 (24.44)	-	64.15 (64.07)	5.01 (4.93)	-	948 (487)	0.79
Ph ₃ Sn(OAr) (C ₃₀ H ₂₄ O ₂ Sn)	Light brown	85	100	23.22 (22.93)	-	69.81 (69.36)	4.70 (4.62)	-	998 (519)	0.51
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ Sn(OAr) (C ₂₄ H ₃₆ O ₂ Sn)	Colourless	86	148*	26.02 (25.93)	-	62.82 (62.74)	7.91 (7.84)	-	981 (459)	0.75
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(OAr).2Imid. (C ₂₆ H ₃₅ ClN ₄ O ₂ Sn)	White	79	72	21.06 (20.75)	6.02 (6.19)	54.10 (54.40)	6.22 (6.10)	9.72 (9.76)	-	0.82
Me ₂ Sn(OAr) ₂ .2Imid. (C ₃₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₂ Sn)	Creamish white	78	93	19.02 (19.10)	-	61.89 (61.64)	5.09 (5.14)	8.27 (8.99)	-	0.71
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(OAr).2Benz. (C ₃₄ H ₃₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ Sn)	White	86	82	17.53 (17.76)	5.13 (5.27)	61.35 (60.58)	5.87 (5.79)	7.29 (8.31)	-	0.95
Me ₂ SnCl(OAr).2Benz. (C ₂₈ H ₂₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ Sn)	Dirty white	75	153	20.08 (20.19)	5.92 (6.02)	56.91 (57.00)	4.17 (4.58)	9.15 (9.50)	-	0.62
Me ₂ SnCl(OAr).2Benz. (C ₄₀ H ₃₆ N ₂ O ₂ Sn)	Yellow	76	80	16.12 (16.46)	-	65.93 (66.39)	4.82 (4.98)	7.48 (7.74)	-	0.26
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ Sn(OAr).Benz. (C ₃₁ H ₃₇ N ₂ O ₂ Sn)	Dark red	88	40	20.12 (20.62)	-	64.62 (64.47)	7.14 (7.28)	4.56 (4.85)	-	0.49

OAr = OC₆H₄-C₆H₅-2; Benz. = C₇H₆N₂; Imid. = C₃H₄N₂.

plexes are quite stable under dry conditions. It is of interest to note that triphenyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxide is a sharp melting solid while dimethyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides are high melting solids. The di- and tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides are high boiling liquids. The complexes are soluble in organic polar solvents, nitrobenzene and nitromethane. The molar conductance values of the millimolar (10^{-3} M) solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene (ranging from 0.56 – $1.1 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) show that all the complexes are non-electrolytic in nature. The molecular weight determinations of the complexes by Rast's camphor method have indicated that except for $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})_2$ which has been found to be monomer, the rest of the complexes exhibit dimeric nature. All attempts to obtain X-ray quality single crystals were unsuccessful.

IR spectra :

In order to ascertain the formation of complexes, the IR spectra of newly synthesized organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides were compared with free 2-phenylphenol. The absorption band at 3653 cm^{-1} in 2-phenylphenol was found to be absent in the complexes indicating deprotonation of phenolic oxygen. The absorption bands occurring in 1327 – 1269 cm^{-1} region in 2-phenylphenol ascribed to $\nu(\text{C}_{\text{phenolic}}\text{-O})^7$ mode appeared at lower frequencies (1240 – 1160 cm^{-1}) region in complexes indicating the involvement of phenolic oxygen atom in bonding. The bonding through phenolic oxygen to tin metal was further supported by the appearance of bands in 480 – 420 cm^{-1} region attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ modes in far-IR region⁸. The sharp bands observed in 670 – 640 cm^{-1} region in complexes excluding $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})_2$ may be ascribed to Sn–O–Sn mode suggesting thereby the dimeric nature of the complexes⁹. The absorption bands observed at 340 and 330 cm^{-1} in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Ph-2})$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Ph-2})$ complexes respectively may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ mode in agreement with earlier reports¹⁰. The absorption bands observed at 590 and 520 cm^{-1} ; 554 and 525 cm^{-1} ; 598 and 515 cm^{-1} ; 280 and 260 cm^{-1} may be assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$ mode¹¹ in case of di-*n*-butyl, dimethyl, tri-*n*-butyl and triphenyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides respectively.

NMR studies :

Further information on the formation of complexes was gathered by recording their ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{119}Sn NMR spectra. The NMR data are listed in Table 2.

^1H NMR spectra :

A comparison of the room temperature ^1H NMR spec-

tra of complexes with that of free 2-phenylphenol substantiated the formation of complexes. The ^1H NMR spectra of 2-phenylphenol displayed signals at δ 5.16, 6.96–7.28 and 7.40–7.53 ppm attributed to phenolic -OH group, aromatic ring and the phenyl substituent protons, respectively. It is pertinent to mention here that spatial geometry of the 2-phenylphenol molecule may be accounted for the assignment of signals due to phenolic ring protons at high field relative to that of the phenyl substituent. The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes did not display any signal at δ 5.16 ppm confirming the deprotonation of phenolic proton. The aromatic protons of the phenolic ring as well as the phenyl substituent were found to undergo downfield shifts in complexes which may be ascribed to deshielding of these protons due to a shift of electron density from the ring to tin metal. The resonances due to *n*-butyl, methyl and phenyl group attached to tin metal in their respective chlorides did not undergo any change upon complexation with 2-phenylphenol. The proton resonances of the butyl and phenyl groups linked to tin appeared as complex patterns, hence couplings could not be resolved. The observed 2J (^{119}Sn – ^1H) coupling constant values for complexes $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}(\text{OAr})$ and $\text{Me}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OAr})_2$ may be ascribed to five-coordinate structure in solution.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

A comparison of ^{13}C NMR spectra of organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides with that of 2-phenylphenol well demonstrated the formation of complexes. The carbon resonances due to phenolic ring occurring in δ 116.0–152.5 ppm and phenyl substituent in δ 130.1–137.3 ppm range in 2-phenylphenol suffered downfield shifts on complexation. The carbon resonances due to organic groups attached to tin, however, remained unaltered in complexes relative to the chloride precursors. The magnitude of coupling constants 1J (^{119}Sn – ^{13}C) for dibutyl and triphenyltin(IV) complexes are indicative of four and five coordinate environment around tin respectively.

^{119}Sn NMR spectra :

The ^{119}Sn NMR signals of organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides, were observed to shift upfield between δ –105 to –162 ppm with respect to the δ (^{119}Sn) values reported to occur at +122, +141, –141 and –44.7 ppm in $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl}_2$, Me_2SnCl_2 , $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{SnCl}$ and Ph_3SnCl respectively¹². The observed trend may be attributed to the fact that replacement of chloride ion by 2-phenylphenoxide ion has resulted in an increased electron density at tin and thereby tin has been shielded in agreement with previous report¹³.

Mass spectra :

The FAB-Mass spectra of complexes of composition $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl(OAr)}$, $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ and $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$ were recorded. The former three complexes displayed molecular ion peaks with 25, 35 and 5% intensity while the latter did not exhibit any molecular ion peak. The appearance of fragment ions higher than m/z though of quite low intensity in case of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl(OAr)}$, $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ complexes are suggestive of their dimeric nature. On the other hand, $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$ has been indicated to exist as monomer. The observance of base peaks corresponding to $[n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}]^+$ and $[n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)(OC}_6\text{H}_5)]^+$ ions in $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ and $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$ respectively, suggested strong Sn-OAr bond. However, in the case of $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl(OAr)}$ and $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$, the $[\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl}]^+$ and $[\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn}]^+$ appeared as the most abundant ions by the cleavage of Sn-OAr bond. The presence of stable isotopes of naturally occurring tin have led to highly characteristic pattern of a group of peaks for tin containing fragments in mass spectra and well defined cleavage sequences.

Though the geometry around tin cannot be ascertained in the absence of Mössbauer and X-Ray crystallographic studies of complexes, yet on the basis of physicochemical and IR, ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{119}Sn NMR and mass spectral data in hand, the following tentative structures for the complexes may be proposed as :

 $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$ **Thermal studies :**

Thermal behaviour of the complexes was studied by TGA-DTA techniques in air and the results obtained from the TG and DTA curves are summarized in Table 3. A

perusal of the data showed that $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{SnCl(OAr)}$, $n\text{-Bu}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$, $\text{Me}_2\text{SnCl(OAr)}$, $\text{Me}_2\text{Sn(OAr)}_2$, $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ and $n\text{-Bu}_3\text{Sn(OAr)}$ complexes displayed initial decomposition temperature at 185.7, 150.0, 119.2, 181.8, 210.0 and 137.8 °C respectively after which temperature, the complexes undergo decomposition in either single or two steps. Strikingly, di-*n*-butyl and triphenyltin(IV) complexes displayed single step decomposition with a continuous weight loss of 100%. The dimethyl and tri-*n*-butyl derivatives, on the other hand, seemed to decompose in two stages for which on the basis of percentage weight losses, the following schemes of decomposition may be proposed as :

The DTA curves of the complexes substantiated the thermal decompositions in TG which were accompanied by both endo- and exothermic peaks.

Lewis acid behaviour :

The reactions of organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides with nitrogenous bases, viz. imidazole (Imid) and benzimidazole (Benz) (L) in 1 : 2 molar ratio afforded metal : base 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 adducts of composition $\text{R}_3\text{Sn(OAr).L}$ and $\text{R}'_2\text{SnCl}_{2-x}(\text{OAr})_x.2\text{L}$ ($\text{R} = \text{Ph}$ and $n\text{-Bu}$) and ($\text{R}' = n\text{-Bu}$ and Me ; $x = 1$ and 2) respectively in conformity with their analytical data (Table 1). The molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of the adducts suggested their non-electrolytic nature.

The infrared spectra of the adducts with imidazole and benzimidazole provided evidences that the ligands L are coordinated monodentately, inferred from the shifts in absorptions relative to those of free ligands. The absorption bands due to $\nu\text{N-H}$ mode appeared in 3199–3192 cm^{-1} region in imidazole and 3118–3110 cm^{-1} region in benzimidazole adducts relative to $\nu\text{N-H}$ mode occurring at 3206 and 3117 cm^{-1} in uncoordinated imidazole and benzimidazole respectively¹⁴. The bands in 1620–1450 cm^{-1} region in free bases due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁵ modes were observed to shift towards higher frequency (1650–1480 cm^{-1}) in the adducts. The observed trend of shifts¹⁶ suggested that the bases (L) are monodentately coordinated through pyridyl nitrogen to tin metal in line with earlier reports¹⁷. In the far-IR spectra, the bands $\sim 380 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be ascribed to $\nu(\text{Sn}\leftarrow\text{N})$ mode¹⁸.

A peculiar feature of the spectra of addition compounds with nitrogenous bases was the absence of bands due to Sn–O–Sn modes observed in dimethyl, triphenyl and tributyltin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides, indicating the breakdown of dimeric structure in the parent complexes upon coordination with bases.

On the basis of above observations, it may tentatively be inferred that the adducts of di-*n*-butyl and dimethyltin(IV) complexes show octahedral geometry around tin while the addition compounds derived from tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) complexes display pentacoordinate structures.

Experimental

All the solvents used were of A.R. grade and were dried by standard methods. 2-Phenylphenol (Merck) was recrystallized from benzene and the purity was checked by its sharp melting point (57 °C). *n*-Bu₂SnCl₂, Me₂SnCl₂, *n*-Bu₃SnCl and Ph₃SnCl were used as received. Imidazole and benzimidazole were of Merck grade.

Tin in complexes was determined gravimetrically as SnO₂ while chlorine was determined by Volhard's method. Elemental analyses were performed on Carlo-Erba 1108 Elemental Analyzer. The conductivity measurements in nitrobenzene were made on an Elico Conductivity Bridge type CM-82T. Molecular weights were determined by Rast's camphor method. FTIR spectra of complexes were collected on Nicolet-Avatar 1000 FTIR spectrophotometer (4000–200 cm⁻¹) as KBr pellets and nujol mull in CsI optics. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL PMX 60 SI spectrometer using CDCl₃ as solvent. The ¹³C NMR spectra of complexes were recorded on Bruker-AC-300 MHz NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃. TMS was used as an internal reference. ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra were obtained using Me₄Sn as an external reference. The FAB mass spectra were recorded at room temperature on JEOL SX 102/DA-600 mass spectrometer/Data system using Ar/Xe (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage

was 10 kV. The *m*-nitrobenzylalcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix. Thermograms were recorded on simultaneous TG-DTA Linseis, L81-11 (German) thermal analyzer. The analytical constants were; heating rate 10 °C min⁻¹, reference Al₂O₃; thermocouple Pt/Pt-Rh 10%.

Preparation of Me₃SiOC₆H₄Ph-2 :

The trimethylsilyl derivative of 2-phenylphenol was prepared by refluxing hexamethyldisilazane (1.23 ml, 6 mmol) with two equivalents of 2-phenylphenol (2.0 g, 12 mmol) in dry CCl₄ till the evolution of ammonia gas ceased. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure to collect the resulting liquid compound. It was then distilled under vacuum (15 mm Hg) (b.p. = 145 °C).

Preparation of *n*-Bu₂SnCl_{2-x}(OC₆H₄Ph-2)_x (where *x* = 1 and 2) :

To a solution of *n*-Bu₂SnCl₂ (3.19 g, 10 mmol) in dry carbon tetrachloride was added an equimolar amount of trimethylsilyl-2-phenylphenoxide (10 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h to ensure the completion of the reaction. The excess of the solvent was evaporated under vacuum. The concentrate was treated with petroleum ether. No solid compound was obtained. The solvent was removed by distillation. The remainder was then distilled off under reduced pressure to collect the colourless liquid (yield, 4.08 g, 89%).

The complex of composition *n*-Bu₂Sn(OC₆H₄Ph-2)₂ was obtained as colourless liquid by adopting the similar method involving the reaction of *n*-Bu₂SnCl₂ (1.596 g, 5 mmol) with bimolar amount of trimethylsilyl-2-phenylphenoxide (10 mmol) in carbon tetrachloride (yield, 2.69 g, 90%).

Preparation of Ph₃Sn(OC₆H₄Ph-2) :

To a solution of Ph₃SnCl (0.408 g, 10 mmol) in dry CCl₄ was added an equimolar amount of the trimethylsilyl derivative of 2-phenylphenol (10 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 h to ensure the completion of reaction. The excess of the solvent was removed by evaporation under vacuum. The concentrate was treated with distilled petroleum ether whereupon the separation of light brown solid resulted. It was dried under vacuum and was recrystallised from 1 : 1 mixture of dichloromethane and acetonitrile (yield, 0.47 g, 85%).

Preparation of Me₂SnCl_{2-x}(OAr)_x (where OAr = OC₆H₄Ph-2; *x* = 1 and 2) :

To a solution of dimethyltin dichloride (2 g, 9 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran was added a solution of 2-phenylphenol (1.547 g, 9 mmol) in the same solvent followed by the

Table 3. Thermal data of organotin(IV) complexes

Complex	Initial decomp. temp. (°C)	Stages of decomp.	TGA data		DTA data		
			Decomp. rang (°C)	%Wt. loss	Decomp. products	Peak temp. (°C)	Peak nature
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(OAr)	185.7	Single	185.7–295.0	100	–	272.2 294.7	Endo Exo
<i>n</i> -Bu ₂ SnCl(OAr) ₂	150.0	Single	150.0–293.4	100	–	247.1 265.1	Endo Exo (fble)
Me ₂ SnCl(OAr)	119.2	Two	119.2–260.3 260.3–412.0	53.32 27.01	Me ₂ SnO 0.5 SnO	186.8 283.9 302.2 317.9 332.5	Endo Endo Exo (fble) Exo Exo
Me ₂ Sn(OAr) ₂	181.8	Two	181.8–270.3 270.3–503.7	66.11 19.60	Me ₂ SnO 0.5 SnO	179.8 435.9 461.8	Endo Exo Exo
Ph ₃ Sn(OAr)	210.0	Single	210.0–384.6	100	–	102.2 312.3 390.1	Endo (sharp) Exo (sharp) Exo (br)
<i>n</i> -Bu ₃ Sn(OAr)	137.8	Single	137.8–500.0	87.0	0.5 SnO	269.5 300.8 312.3 431.6	Exo Exo Exo Exo

dropwise addition of an equimolar amount of diethylamine (0.947 ml, 9 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h at room temperature when a quantitative amount of white solid, identified as diethylaminehydrochloride, separated out. The solid was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated under vacuum. The concentrate was then treated with petroleum ether and was kept as such overnight. The yellow solid thus obtained was dried under vacuum and was then recrystallized from diethyl ether (yield, 2.28 g, 71%).

The complex of composition Me₂Sn(OC₆H₄Ph-2)₂ was prepared by the similar method involving the reaction of Me₂SnCl₂ (2 g, 9 mmol) with 2-phenylphenol (3.0954 g, 18 mmol) and diethylamine (1.90 ml, 18 mmol). The work up of the reaction gave a creamish white solid (yield, 3.4 g, 77%).

Preparation of *n*-Bu₃Sn(OC₆H₄Ph-2) :

To a solution of *n*-tributyltin chloride (2.393 ml, 7 mmol) in tetrahydrofuran was added a solution of 2-phenylphenol (1.249 g, 7 mmol) in the same solvent followed by the dropwise addition of diethylamine (0.76 ml, 7 mmol). The mixing of the reactants resulted in an instantaneous separation of white solid identified as diethylaminehydrochloride. The reaction mixture was

stirred for 24 h at room temperature to ensure the completion of the reaction. The solid formed was removed by filtration. The filtrate was then treated with petroleum ether and was kept as such overnight. No separation of any solid was observed. The addition of other organic solvents also did not yield any solid. The excess of the solvent was distilled off. The remaining liquid was then distilled under vacuum to obtain colourless liquid compound (yield, 2.90 g, 86%).

Preparation of adducts :

The adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of bimolar amounts of nitrogenous bases with parent organotin(IV) 2-phenylphenoxides in suitable solvents (THF + MeOH/THF) by stirring at room temperature for 12 h in separate experiments. The reaction mixture was then concentrated under vacuum and the solid product was isolated by the addition of petroleum ether. It was filtered, washed several times with petroleum ether and was dried in vacuo.

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